

Supplementary Material 5

Weighted correlation between male relative reproductive success and relative body length

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To compute the weighted correlation between the male relative reproductive success and the relative body length, we fitted a linear model of the normalized relative reproductive success as a function of the normalized relative body length which we weighted by the number of days each seal spent at the Rivière du Nord site. In this case, the slope coefficient represents the correlation between both variables as they are normalized (i.e., divided by their standard deviation).

1 The model equation

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_i + \epsilon_i$$

$$\epsilon_i \sim Normal(0, \sigma_\epsilon^2)$$

y_i is the relative reproductive success of the breeding male i , β_0 is the intercept, β_1 is the slope associated with the relative body length which represents the correlation between both variable as they are normalized (i.e., divided by their standard deviation), and ϵ_i is the residual value which follows a normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a variance of σ_ϵ^2 .

2 load the data

We load the data with 57 individuals into the variable `dat` from the file `data_SR_model.txt`, which can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7418941>

```
head(dat)
```

```
##      Name      Id N_pups Female Male      Length Length_se Tenure  Success
## 1: Nombril M001-B-17    15      8    7 0.85536932 0.1842269    40 1.5862709
## 2: Flamby  M002-B-17     1      1    0 2.36481609 0.2526274     1 0.1057514
```

## 3:	Y M003-B-17	66	31	35	0.07695452	0.1346348	54	6.9795918
## 4:	Five M004-B-17	36	18	18	0.97141528	0.1213637	44	3.8070501
## 5:	Cratere M005-B-17	23	11	12	0.31615580	0.1515888	51	2.4322820
## 6:	Luffy M006-B-17	4	3	1	0.21161909	0.1839906	42	0.4230056

- Name: the seal unique name
- Id: the seal unique identifier
- N_pups: total number of pups produced by breeding seals
- Female: number of daughters produced by breeding seals
- Male: number of sons produced by breeding seals
- Length: relative body length of the seals
- Length_se: standard error associated with each value of Length
- Tenure: number of days a seal spent at the Rivière du Nord breeding site
- Success: relative reproductive success, i.e., the number of pups produced by the focal seal divided by the mean number of pups produced in the population

3 Fit the model with brms

From previous studies on elephant seals, the reproductive success of breeding males is positively correlated with their body size (McCann, 1981; Clinton and Le Boeuf, 1993; Haley et al., 1994; Modig, 1996; Carlini et al., 2006; Galimberti et al., 2007). For example, Modig (1996) found a correlation of 0.32 and Haley et al. (1994) an average correlation of 0.41 between male length and copulation success. Based on these studies, we defined the prior distribution of the slope coefficient of the linear model (i.e., the correlation between the relative reproductive success and the relative body length of the males) by a normal distribution with a mean of 0.35 and a standard deviation of 0.1. And we used a normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 0.1 for the intercept coefficient. We also weighed the model by the Tenure of each seal, which in brms multiplies the log-likelihood of each observation by the corresponding weight value.

Figure S1: The histograms of the informative prior distributions for each of the model parameters: (β_0) the intercept, (β_1) the slope associated with the male relative body length.

```
## normalize variables
dat$Success <- scale(dat$Success)
dat$Length <- scale(dat$Length)

# load brms R package (v2.15.0)
library("brms")

bprior <- prior(normal(0, 0.1), class = "b", coef = "Intercept") +
  prior(normal(0.35, 0.1), class = "b", coef = "Length")
```

```
fit <- brm(Success|weights(Tenure, scale=TRUE) ~ 0 + Intercept + Length,
          data      = dat,
          family    = gaussian(),
          prior     = bprior,
          chain     = 4,
          core      = 4,
          iter      = 20000,
          thin      = 4,
          seed      = 5477)
```

4 brms output summary

No divergent transitions were reported when fitting the model with the function `brm()`. The correlation between the male relative reproductive success and the relative body length weighted by the tenure (i.e., the number of days each seal spent at the Rivière du Nord breeding site) is 0.4 ± 0.09 [0.23, 0.57].

```
## Family: gaussian
## Links: mu = identity; sigma = identity
## Formula: Success | weights(Tenure, scale = TRUE) ~ 0 + Intercept + Length
## Data: dat (Number of observations: 57)
## Samples: 4 chains, each with iter = 20000; warmup = 10000; thin = 4;
##          total post-warmup samples = 10000
##
## Population-Level Effects:
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## Intercept      0.03      0.05  -0.06   0.12 1.00     9311     8823
## Length         0.40      0.09   0.23   0.57 1.00    10179    10015
##
## Family Specific Parameters:
##           Estimate Est.Error 1-95% CI u-95% CI Rhat Bulk_ESS Tail_ESS
## sigma       1.16      0.11   0.96   1.40 1.00     9946     9848
##
## Samples were drawn using sampling(NUTS). For each parameter, Bulk_ESS
## and Tail_ESS are effective sample size measures, and Rhat is the potential
## scale reduction factor on split chains (at convergence, Rhat = 1).
```

References

- Carlini, A. R., Poljak, S., Daneri, G. A., Márquez, M. E. I., and Negrete, J. (2006). The dynamics of male harem dominance in southern elephant seals (*Mirounga leonina*) at the South Shetland Islands. *Polar Biology*, 29(9):796–805.
- Clinton, W. L. and Le Boeuf, B. J. (1993). Sexual selection’s effects on male life history and the pattern of male mortality. *Ecology*, 74(6):1884–1892.
- Galimberti, F., Sanvito, S., Braschi, C., and Boitani, L. (2007). The cost of success: Reproductive effort in male southern elephant seals (*Mirounga leonina*). *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, 62(2):159–171.
- Haley, M. P., Deutsch, C. J., and Le Boeuf, B. J. (1994). Size, dominance and copulatory success in male northern elephant seals, *Mirounga angustirostris*. *Animal Behaviour*, 48(6):1249–1260.
- McCann, T. S. (1981). Aggression and sexual activity of male southern elephant seals, *Mirounga leonina*. *Journal of Zoology*, 195:295–310.

Modig, A. (1996). Effects of body size and harem size on male reproductive behaviour in the southern elephant seal. *Animal Behaviour*, 51(6):1295–1306.